

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 (2022)

PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

Supervisory Styles and Teacher Commitment: Implications for Pedagogical Quality

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Article Information

Received: October 31, 2022

Accepted: November 14, 2022

Published: November 28, 2022

Keywords

Teacher Commitment, Teacher Education, Supervision, Leadership, Pedagogy

ABSTRACT

Ghanaians have expressed worries about the commitment of teachers at public pre-tertiary schools, which has resulted in falling educational standards in the country. Ghanaians have highlighted poor supervision as the primary cause of teachers' commitment, resulting in students' poor academic performance in external examination. The present study examined supervisory styles and teacher commitment in senior high schools. Using three senior high schools in a Municipality in the Bono region of Ghana as the point of call, this paper provides empirical insights on whether or not supervisory styles of headteachers affect teacher commitment. 152 teachers were sampled using the proportionate sampling technique. The findings indicated that all the supervisory types were perceived to be practiced in the schools. Inquiry-based supervision, however, was adjudged the most practiced supervisory type in the schools. The findings show that only clinical supervision significantly contributes to the prediction of teacher commitment in schools. It was recommended, among other things, that school heads create a working environment that is more supportive, caring, and positive, which provides a space for regular communication, problem-solving and pedagogical quality.

INTRODUCTION

The mere improvement in educational resources does not increase the quality of education, rather, good administration of these resources at the school level, maintaining an effective system of professional supervision, and avoiding the degradation of vital support structures for teachers, according to Esia-Donkoh and Ofori-Dwamena (2014). As a result, in order for educational institutions to meet their objectives, a framework for continuous oversight of the institutions' operations, particularly in the instructional process, must be established (Hismanoglu & Hismanoglu, 2010).

Educational stakeholders must oversee educational practices in order to achieve consistent positive results in order to provide a proactive and quality educational system for individual community and national progress, according to U-Sayee and Adomako (2021). As a result, stable supervision methods are essential for quality and efficient education (Okendu, 2012). Supervisory assessment of teaching staff helps educators get the support they need to thrive, examine and balance the benefits and drawbacks of different educational methodologies and initiatives, and ensure great student achievement in schools (Ngole & Mkulu, 2021).

The effectiveness of instructional supervision in schools is likely to influence instructors' competence, practice, work satisfaction, and student learning outcomes. Furthermore, Khalid, Komuji, and Veloo (2013) claimed that properly monitoring can improve teachers' teaching effectiveness, which is critical for improving students' learning development. Also, according to Mwesiga and Okendo (2018), heads of schools have numerous tasks

to enforce teachers' teaching commitments, including influencing, motivating, and assisting followers in achieving established educational goals.

Statement of the Problem

Yeng, Woode-Eshun, and Badu (2022), aver that there has been a considerable public outcry in recent decades regarding falling educational standards, particularly in student academic performance during external examinations in Ghana. Poor supervision has been highlighted as the primary cause of students' poor academic performance in external examinations. Although the Ghanaian government is working to improve school supervision, more work has to be done. Informal discussions in society and related research findings indicate that poor student performance in public schools is partly the result of inefficient teacher supervision. The problem of inefficient teacher supervision has been with Ghana over decades, a non-governmental organisation in Ghana, the Integrated Social Development Centre (ISODEC) in 2011 indicated that most teachers, knowing that they are not closely supervised, do not attend school on a regular basis to teach or provide substandard instruction, thereby compromising educational standards. Unlike previous studies which tackle the problem by looking at teachers' attitude toward supervision, challenges of supervision and the effect of supervision on teacher, this study looked at the types of supervision practiced in the schools and the type of supervision which affects the commitment of teachers. Altun's (2017) research examined how committed teachers affect student performance, emphasises the differences these teachers

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make, and identifies how passionate teachers impact effective teaching and learning. What seems missing in the literature is whether or not the supervisory styles of headteachers, in any way, influence teacher commitment. It is on this note that this present study sought to bridge the lacuna by examining the nexus between supervisory styles and teacher commitment.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study sought to answer following questions:

- 1) What do headteachers practice the dominant supervisory styles?
- 2) What supervisory style(s) affect the commitment of senior high school teachers?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Supervision

It is believed that an effective supervisor can be an organizations' most valuable asset. A well-trained supervisor who excels at managing employees can make everyone around them more effective and efficient.

School supervision, is defined by Eregie and Ogiamen (2007) as a full mechanism methodically structured to achieve the aim of education, so that the internal structure of the school is dictated by the functions that are carried out towards those ends. The overall goal of supervision is to improve teaching and learning in schools. The fundamental principle of supervision is that a teacher's instructional behaviour has an impact on student learning. According to Adu, Akinloye, and Olaoye (2014), the ultimate goal of supervision is to increase the institutions' overall efficiency and academic standards. Instructional supervision's goal is to assist teachers in identifying their problems and finding the best solutions, whether they are individual or group issues.

Teachers' difficulties and issues with teaching and learning differ, as do their needs and interests (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). Instructional supervision procedures must be adjusted to the individual needs of each supervised teacher. Because adapting supervisory tactics to individual needs is likely to increase teachers' passion and commitment at work (Benjamin, 2014). Sullivan and Glanz (2010) proved that the correct usage of numerous supervision approaches can boost teachers' professional growth and improve instructional efficiency by supporting the need for alternative supervisory alternatives for teachers. There are at least five forms of supervision, according to Sergiovanni and Starratt (2007): Clinical, Collegial, Self-Directed, Informal and Inquiry-Based Supervision.

Clinical Supervision

Clinical supervision refers to face-to-face contact with teachers to improve instruction and increase professional growth (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). According to Paba (2017), clinical supervision is a formative evaluation procedure that includes planning conferences, class

observations, and feedback conferences. This form of supervision is intended to improve teaching techniques. Clinical supervision is used by supervisors who collaborate with teachers and provide expert support to teachers in order to improve instruction. Clinical supervision aims to assist teachers in modifying existing teaching patterns in ways that make sense to them and meet agreed-upon material or teaching standards (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). The supervisor's purpose here is to assist the teacher in selecting goals to be implemented, illuminating teaching challenges, and better understanding his or her practice.

Collegial Supervision

Partnerships, peer and collaborative relationships, coaching and mentoring are names that are given to the supervision practices in which learning, growing and changing are the mutual focus for supervisors and teachers (Beach & Reinhartz, 2010). According to Allan Glatthorn, this technique is a "moderately organized process through which two or more teachers agree to collaborate for their own professional improvement, typically by watching one other's classrooms, providing feedback on the observations, and addressing common professional concerns." (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). According to Sergiovanni and Starratt (2007), Collegial supervision extends beyond classroom observation. It provides an informal forum for instructors to discuss difficulties, share ideas, assist one another in class preparation, exchange advice, and provide additional assistance to one another.

Self-directed Supervision

Teachers in self-directed supervision work independently and are responsible for their own professional development. According to Sergiovanni and Starratt (2007), teachers might prepare a yearly plan containing targets or goals based on an assessment of their own needs. This strategy could then be distributed to supervisors or other individuals. Teachers should be given a lot of latitude in constructing the plan as the process progresses, but supervisors should ensure that the plan and selected development targets are both practical and attainable. Supervisor and instructor meet at the conclusion of a set term, usually a year, to discuss the teacher's progress toward professional development goals. Teachers will be required to submit evidence, such as time logs, reflective practice diaries, schedules, photo essays, cassettes, samples of students' work, and other artefacts that demonstrate progress toward goals

Informal Supervision

Informal supervision comprises causal encounters between supervisors and teachers and is characterized by frequent informal visits to teacher's classroom; conversation with teachers about their work, and other informal activities. Typically, no appointments are made and classroom visits are not announced. In selecting

additional options, supervisors should accommodate teacher preferences and honour them in nearly every case, (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007).

Inquiry-based Supervision

As pairs or teams of teachers work together to address challenges, inquiry-based supervision in the form of action research is an option that can represent an individual initiative or a joint effort. Sergiovanni & Starratt (2007) describe action research as a process aimed at discovering new ideas or practices and testing old ones, exploring or establishing relationships between cause and effect, or systematically gaining evidence about the nature of a particular problem.

Yeng, Woode-Eshun, and Badu (2022) conducted a study on how public basic schools handle school supervision. According to the data, clinical supervision (M=4.03, SD=0.71) predominated over training and guiding supervision (M=3.84, SD=0.69), collegial supervision (M=2.73, SD=0.67), and traditional supervision (M=2.65, SD=0.80). On the other hand, it was found that all aspects of school monitoring were present in all schools. Baffour-Awuah (2011) aimed to elucidate the practice of instructional supervision by examining teachers’ and head teachers’ concepts, perspectives, and experience with instructional supervision. The study sample consisted of 250 teachers, 50 head teachers, and 2 administrators in Ghana.

The study used a mixed-method approach (descriptive analysis methodology) and employed a questionnaire, interviews, and analysis of the Ghana Education Service policy document on supervision as tools for the study. The study concluded that the policy document on instructional supervision, which emphasizes aspects of instructional supervision related to monitoring teaching activities and ensuring maximum use of instructional time, may have a

negative impact on instructional supervision.

Teacher Commitment

Teacher commitment is an intrinsic factor that motivates instructors to continue their involvement in the school by devoting more time and effort to it. This readiness to support the school fosters an emotional bond between instructors and the institution, which in turn motivates them to look for methods to advance their careers as teachers and create a productive learning environment that enables students to achieve their goals (Altun, 2017). A key element in raising children’s success levels is teacher dedication. It must be noted that the requirement for high-quality learning and instruction is crucial since passion also has a motivating impact. Passion involves seeking out and experimenting with the novel. The foundation of effective teaching is passion. The desire of teachers to support students and assume responsibility for their education is embraced by the concept of teacher commitment to learners. In order to improve learners’ educational experiences, educators have a responsibility to research cutting-edge instructional strategies.

Materials and Methods

Population

The population was made up of teachers who had taught for more than two years. This is because these categories of respondents may be aware of the nuances on supervision in their respective schools.

Sampling Size and Procedure

Using Krejcie and Morgan’s table for sample size determination, a sample size of at least 152 was required. The sample selected was distributed proportionally for the various schools. The proposed sampled respondents are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Sampled Respondents for the Study

Strata	Sample Frame	Sample Size
School A	45	45/250×152 = 27
School B	100	100/250×152 = 61
School C	105	105/250×152 = 64
Total	250	152

Measurements

The study used close-ended questionnaires. Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (regression analysis) were produced. Specifically, the descriptive analyses method was adopted to analyses Objective One. Here, the central tendencies and measures of dispersions of the various response items were measured to provide understanding on the extent of the convergence of the responses. The Objective two was analyzed based on an inferential statistic method. Specifically, standard multiple regression analysis was used to establish the form of supervision that affects the commitment of senior high school teachers. The model specify for the study was:

$$TP = \beta_0 + \beta_1CLISUP + \beta_2COLSUP + \beta_3SDSUP + \beta_4INFSUP + \beta_5INQSUB + \epsilon$$

TC = Teacher Commitment

CLISUP = Clinical Supervision

COLSUP = Collegial Supervision

SDSUP = Self-Directed Supervision

INFSUP = Informal Supervision

INQSUP = Inquiry-based supervision

ϵ = Error term

Findings

Types of Supervision Practiced

To measure respondents’ views on the type of supervision practiced in the schools, the five main types of supervision,

namely; clinical supervision, collegial supervision, self-directed supervision, informal supervision, and inquiry-based supervision were considered. On a 5-point scale with 1 being a minimum score and 5 being a maximum

score, a mean score of 0-2.5 is considered low, between 2.51 and 3.51 is considered moderate (average) and above 3.51 is considered high (Okorley, 2010). The results obtained are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Types of Supervision of Teaching and Learning

Supervision Type	Mean	Std. Dev.
Clinical supervision	3.5654	1.10247
Collegial supervision	3.7173	.99137
Self-directed supervision	3.6545	1.06917
Informal supervision	3.7016	.98939
Inquiry-based supervision	4.0838	.79690

As shown in table 2, inquiry-based supervision was identified as the type of supervision teachers perceived to be the most practiced as it has the highest mean score of 4.0838. The respondents seem consistent with their response in terms of inquiry-based supervision as it could be seen from the least standard deviation of .79690. This implies that the various schools mostly practice supervision in the form of action research which is an option that can represent an individual initiative or a collaborative effort as pairs or teams of teachers work together to solve problems. These findings, however, contradict that of Yeng, Woode-Eshun, and Badu (2022) who found that clinical supervision predominated over other forms of supervision in Ghanaian Basic schools. Again, from Table 2, the respondents indicated that Clinical supervision (M=3.5654, SD=1.10247), Collegial supervision (M=3.7173, SD=.99137), Self-directed supervision (M=3.6545, SD=1.06917), and Informal supervision (M=3.7016, SD=.98939) were all supervision types that respondents perceived to be practiced.

Types of Supervision that affects the Commitment of Teachers

As previously mentioned, there are five basic techniques to carry out supervision: clinical supervision, collegial supervision, self-directed supervision, informal supervision, and inquiry-based supervision. The independent variables were the five types. Additionally, all of the commitment indicators for teachers were combined into a single score and utilized as the dependent variable. The dependent variable was then regressed against the independent factors. The coefficient of determination (R²), standard errors, and associated significant levels were used to base the assessment on the beta (B and β) values (p-values). The standard alpha level of 0.05 was used for the study's objectives. Table 3, Table 4, and Table 5 give the results of the regression analysis.

a. Predictors: (Constant), Inquiry-based supervision, Informal supervision, Clinical supervision, Self-directed supervision, Collegial supervision b. Dependent Variable: Teacher Commitment The model correlation coefficient (R) value of 0.386 indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between the dependent variable

Table 3: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error
1	.386 ^a	.149	.118	.56901

and the independent variables. The R-square value was 0.149, which indicates that the model predicts 14.9% of the variations in teacher's commitment as the dependent variable while the remaining 86.1% is being explained by other variables not included in the model.

Table 4: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	7.865	5	1.573	4.859	.000 ^b
Residual	45.004	139	.324		
Total	52.869	144			

- a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Commitment
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Inquiry-based supervision, Informal supervision, Clinical supervision, Self-directed supervision, Collegial supervision. This F statistic tests the joint significance of the independent variable in explaining the dependent variable. In this analysis, the p-value is well below .05 (p<.000). Therefore, it can be concluded that the R and R² between supervision and teacher's commitment is statistically significant. The implication is that the independent variables, clinical supervision, collegial supervision, self-directed supervision, informal supervision, and inquiry-based supervision significantly predicts or explains the dependent variable, teachers' commitment.

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Commitment

*Sig<0.05, **Sig<0.01, ***Sig<0.001

The results of the supervision style on teacher commitment based on a standardized multiple regression analysis. Clinical supervision reported a beta coefficient of 0.201 and a p-value of 0.000. Collegial supervision recorded a beta coefficient of -0.018 and a p-value of 0.762. Self-directed supervision recorded a beta of 0.032 and p-value of 0.497. Informal supervision recorded a beta of 0.040 and a p-value of 0.427. Inquiry-based supervision also reported a beta of -0.043 and a p-value of 0.762.

Table 5: Standardized Multiple Regression Analysis Summary for Supervision Styles Predicting Teachers' Commitment

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-stats	P-Value
Constant	3.221	.319		10.113	.000
Clinical supervision	.201	.051	.364	3.960	.000***
Collegial supervision	-.018	.058	-.029	-.304	.762
Self-directed supervision	.032	.048	.058	.681	.497
Informal supervision	.040	.050	.069	.796	.427
Inquiry-based supervision	-.043	.064	-.056	-.673	.762

The statistics shows that clinical supervision had the largest unstandardized beta whilst collegial supervision had the smallest unstandardized beta. It implies that clinical supervision makes the strongest unique contribution to explaining teacher commitment, when the variance explained by all other variables in the model is controlled. Also, collegial supervision makes the lowest unique contribution to explaining the dependent variable, teachers' commitment, when the variance explained by all other variables in the model is controlled.

The finding depicts that only clinical supervision significantly contributes to the prediction of teacher commitment. Clinical supervision had a positive beta (B) coefficient of .201 and it was statistically significant at 0.1% level of significance. The reason is that the p-value of clinical supervision (0.000) is lesser than the alpha value (0.001). The beta coefficient value of .201 implies that for every unit improvement or effective in the clinical supervision at the schools, the teachers' commitment will increase by 20%. This finding is consistent with that of Hoque, Kenayathulla, Subramaniam, and Islam (2020), who found that only directive supervision (clinical supervision) was favourably and significantly related to teachers' commitment and attitude.

CONCLUSION

Supervision is essential for the continuous improvement in teacher commitment. This, notwithstanding, the current study's findings indicate that supervision can predict 14.9% of the variation in teacher commitment. This raises concern about other factors that are likely to improve teacher commitment. These other factors must be of concern to stakeholders. These factors may include motivation, training and development amongst others. All five types of supervision are practiced in the school.

Recommendations

It is recommended that the emphasis be placed only on advanced supervisory styles to cope with the changing educational environment as not all the supervisory types positively impact teachers' commitment. For instance, in this study, only clinical supervision positively impacted teachers' commitment. So instead on focusing on all the five, the schools could concentrate on clinical supervision. By fostering continual communication between the supervisor and the teacher to enhance the teaching and learning processes, supervision accords equal emphasis to both students and teachers (Al-Saud, 2007). Teachers

become more productive and efficient thanks to their ongoing learning.

REFERENCES

Adu, E. O., Akinloye, G. M., & Olaoye, O. F. (2014). Internal and external school supervision: Issues, challenges and way forward. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 7(2), 269-278.

Altun, M. (2017). The effects of teacher commitment on student achievement: A case study in Iraq. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(11), 417-426.

Baffour-Awuah, P. (2011). Supervision of instruction in public primary schools in Ghana: *Teacher's and head teacher's perspectives*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Graduate Studies, Murdoch University.

Beach, D. M., & Reinhartz J. (2010). Supervisory leadership: *Focus on instruction*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon

Benjamin, B. A. (2014). Solution-focused supervision: *a resource-oriented approach to developing clinical expertise*.

Eregie, A. E., & Ogiamen, V. O. (2007). School supervision and administrative techniques in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Knowledge Review*, 15(7), 83-87.

Esia-Donkoh, K., & Ofori-Dwamena, E. (2014). Effects of educational supervision on professional development: Perception of public basic school teachers at Winneba, Ghana. *British Journal of Education*, 2(6), 63-82.

Hismanoglu, M., & Hismanoglu, S. (2010). English language teachers' perceptions of educational supervision in relation to their professional development: A case study of Northern Cyprus. *Novitas-Royals (Research on Youth and Language)*, 4(1), 16-34.

Hoque, K. E., Bt Kenayathulla, H. B., D/O Subramaniam, M. V., & Islam, R. (2020). Relationships between supervision and teachers' performance and attitude in secondary schools in Malaysia. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 2158244020925501.

Mwesiga, A., & Okendo, E. O. (2018). Effectiveness of heads of schools in supervising teachers' teaching activities in secondary schools in Kagera region Tanzania. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 6(4), 91-117.

Ngole, D. M., & Mkulu, D. G. (2021). The role of school heads' supervision in improving quality of teaching and learning: a case of public secondary school in

- Ilemela district Mwanza Tanzania. *Int. J. Engl. Literat. Soci. Sci*, 6(1), 59-73.
- Okendu, J. N. (2012). The influence of instructional process and supervision on academic performance of secondary school students of Rivers State, Nigeria. *Academic Research International*, 3(1), 332.
- Paba, L. A. (2017). Clinical Supervision, a Proposal for Ensuring the Effectiveness of English Language Teaching at Public Universities in Colombia. *English Language Teaching*, 10(9), 171-180.
- Sergiovanni, T. J., & Starratt, R. J. (2007). The supervisor's educational platform. *Supervision: A redefinition*.
- Sullivan, S., & Glanz, J. (2010). Alternative approaches to Supervision: Cases from the field. *Journal of Curriculum and Supervision*, 15(3), 212-35.
- U-Sayee, C. R., & Adomako, E. B. (2021). Supervisory practices and challenges faced by senior high school principals in Greater Monrovia, Liberia: *implications for quality education*. *Heliyon*, 7(4).
- Veloo, A., Komuji, M. M. A., & Khalid, R. (2013). The effects of clinical supervision on the teaching performance of secondary school teachers. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 93, 35-39.
- Yeng, E., Woode-Eshun, A., & Badu, S. (2022). Assessment Of Supervision in Public Basic Schools in Northern Ghana: The Case of Lambussie-Karni District. *British Journal of Education*, 10(1), 17-34.